

Religious Freedom With Chinese Characteristics: Successful Strategic Communication for International Churches

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Abstract

While economic studies have coined the catchphrase “socialism with Chinese characteristics,” the importance of “religious freedom with Chinese characteristics” remains undervalued and overlooked. Consistently a significant factor influencing international conflict, religion must be considered an integral part of any holistic analysis of the growing tension between the People’s Republic of China and the United States. The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, headquartered in the United States, continues to grow internationally and has become an important case study demonstrating the strain caused by the arrival of a foreign religion in China. This analysis will describe the context and history of religious freedom in China, presenting the three most important factors influencing the religious perspective of the Chinese Communist Party: rule of law; foreign oppression; and collectivism. An analysis of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints’ approach to strategic communication in China, including recommendations for foreign churches operating in China, will be provided.

Keywords: religious freedom, Chinese Communist Party, Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, strategic communication, State Administration of Religious Affairs

Religious Freedom With Chinese Characteristics

From a western perspective, religious freedom in The People’s Republic of China could easily be construed as inadequate and oppressive. However, initial cursory observation of religious restriction in China eventually gives way to a more intricate, nuanced, complex, comprehensive understanding unrecognized by “East vs West” dogmatism. While the Chinese Communist Party maintains many restrictions on the practice of religion (US State Department, 2022; Human Rights Watch, 2022; Albert & Maizland, 2020), the circumstances of religious practice as portrayed in contemporary western media is often ethnocentric and naturally defensive, consistently ignoring anything positive. Unsanctioned religions currently function in China and, therefore, must utilize sound strategic communication principles in order to effectively grow within the constraints

established by the government.

The following analysis will describe the culture, context, and history through which the Chinese Communist Party views religious freedom, presenting the three most important factors influencing religious perspective in China: rule of law; foreign oppression; and collectivism. Then, a case-study of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints’ approach to religious practice and strategic communication in China will be analyzed, and recommendations for foreign religions will be provided.

Culture & Context

Religious freedom in China is governed by oriental culture and context very different from Western expectations (Cook, 2017; Carpenter & den Dulk, 2014). Just as China’s economic system is neither entirely communist

nor capitalist, so too China's restriction of religion is a hybrid mixture of systems. While economics in China functions as "socialism with Chinese characteristics" (Deng, 1978; Li, 1995; He, 2001; Qiao Collective, 2021), similarly, a structure of "religious freedom with Chinese characteristics" functions in a format, culture, and context unfamiliar to much of western society, neither completely free nor completely restrictive.

It is true that there are five state-sanctioned religions in China: Daoism, Buddhism, Islam, Christianity, and Protestantism (Yang, 2012). However, this does not mean other religions are not present in Chinese society. Similar to economic oligopolies where state-sponsored programs and public enterprises function alongside one another, the religious oligopoly system in China allows for multiple categories of religious operation, both state-sponsored and not (Yang, 2007). Foremost authority on religion in China, Dr. Fenggang Yang of Purdue University, describes these categories as the "Red, Black, and Gray Markets of religion" in China (2006). The Red Market consists of state-sponsored religions, or the five main religions administered by the Chinese Communist Party. The Black Market refers to religions expressly banned and restricted, including groups like The Shouters Sect and Falun Gong (Yang & Pettit, 2018). And the world-wide trend of religious pluralism has led to the emergence of a Gray Market, religion neither sponsored nor criminalized but tolerated by the Chinese Communist Party (Yang, 2010). These unregistered, legally ambiguous, Gray Market religions, although operating in less than ideal circumstances, still experience some freedoms and opportunities for advancement, especially during the current unexpected religious resurgence in China (Cao, 2018).

While many questions remain regarding religious restriction of Falun Gong followers, Uighur and Tibetan minorities, Hong Kong, Macau, and Taiwan (US State Department, 2022), it is clear Chinese culture allows at least some space for religious practice. Because of the space provided by "religious freedom with Chinese characteristics" and because of the Gray Market, how international religions practice and present themselves in China is crucial to their success. Foreign churches must practice effective strategic communication in order to operate effectively in China.

To understand the Chinese Communist Party's contemporary approach to religious freedom, one must understand the history, culture, and context of religious regulation in China. This perspective is built upon at least three interrelated factors influencing the framework

used by the government and people of China: First, the rule of law; second, the fear of foreign oppression; and, third, the culture of collectivism. Successful international religions will adjust strategic communication practices based on these important factors.

Rule of Law vs Rule by Law

Rule of law refers to system governed by a written legal code to which all people and circumstances are subject. Conversely, rule by law refers to a governing body utilizing legal code to promote social stability (Dicey, 1915). *Rule of law* is generally considered to be associated with European conceptualizations of government, whereas rule by law is more prevalent in Asia (World Justice Project, 2021). Neither the general Chinese populace nor government base decisions on the assumption that government leaders are beholden to judicial systems; leaders are simply expected to benevolently use law as a tool to administer social stability. Most scholarly work published in the West includes scathing condemnation of any system not based on the foundational assumption that written law is designed to outline the scope of governmental power, and it is clear Chinese culture does not adhere to this assumption. However, rather than debate which is more efficient, rule of law vs rule by law, this analysis simply acknowledges that China's rule by law culture is the current reality in which foreign religions operate at this time (World Justice Report, 2021).

This discussion is significant because foreign religions often enter China expecting the same rule of law assumptions under which they comfortably operated at home in countries of the West. They are often surprised when characteristics inherent to the rule of law system (such as: open government, accountability, impartial judiciary; see World Justice Project, 2021) manifest differently than unconsciously anticipated. For example, prior to operating in country, some religions may expect a formal legally-binding written declaration documenting legal status from China's State Administration of Religious Affairs (SARA). However, since SARA has yet to legalize any religion or church since the original five state-sanctioned religions were established in the 1950's (Cook, 2017), this is unrealistic. As previously stated, many religious organizations currently operate in China without full governmental recognition (Yang, 2007).

The Chinese culture of rule by law influences the perspective of the purpose and function of written legal documents. While western constitutions are designed to outline and restrict the powers of government, the Chinese perceive written constitutions as a tool utilized

by leaders to accomplish government purposes rather than legally binding restrictions to reign in potentially malevolent government leaders. In fact, the Chinese Constitution explicitly provides for freedom of religion but this is not perceived as establishing governmental limits on religious restriction (Zheng, 2014). Article 36 of the Chinese Constitution is referred to as the “Freedom of Religious Belief Clause” (Fu, 2021), and explicitly states “Citizens of the People’s Republic of China enjoy freedom of religious belief. No state organ, public organization or individual may compel citizens to believe in, or not believe in, any religion...The state protects normal religious activities” (People’s Republic of China Const. art. XXXVI). However, the Chinese interpretation of this clause is seen as giving the government power and authority to promote religious and political stability when Western nations might see this as a restriction placed on government.

This perspective is further affirmed by the clause’s overall placement in the constitution; this article only comes after extensive description and discussion of the rights and powers of the Chinese communist party. As stated by Zheng (2014):

There is a hierarchy of values in the Chinese Constitution...which ranks the supremacy of the Communist Party and the construction of a modern socialist society above the protection of personal freedoms. Indeed, the term ‘protection’ is transformed into something more akin to management and control in the Chinese context. (p. 79)

Although explicitly protected in written constitution, the rule by law ideology dictates that the power of the Party supersedes protection of religious freedom. This “Party-first” mentality must be understood and respected by international religions.

Regardless, it is still meaningful to note that freedom of religious belief is certainly explicitly mentioned in the Chinese Constitution. Chinese leaders are committed to protecting freedom of religion, even if not with as much zeal as protecting the power and stability of governance. Churches not threatening stability have been tolerated.

So, it has been established that there are non-state religions functioning in China permitted under rule by law principles, and the Chinese Constitution provides space for, at least, some degree of religious protection. The next question to consider, then, is “which religions have been restricted by the Chinese government?” Religions on which bans or restricted have been enforced broadly fit in two generalized categories: First, international religions perceived as ‘external’ and posing a foreign threat. And, second, domestic religions threatening internal stability and Chinese nationalism. Note how closely these two categories relate with the following two headings: fear of foreign oppression and culture of collectivism.

Fear of Foreign Oppression

State regulation of religion has, at least partially, been driven by fear of foreign influence (Chang, 2018). Considering the contemporary history of China’s interaction with foreign religion, it is not surprising the Chinese Communist Party is skeptical of foreign influence and remains officially atheistic (Albert & Maizland, 2020).

During the 1800s, several wars and rebellions crippled Chinese stability. The First and Second Opium wars displayed a blatant clash between

Figure 1
World Justice Report 2021 Adherence to Rule of Law

Figure 2
2021 World Justice Report for China, 0 is lowest score and 1 is highest score

Christianity and the Chinese state (Sneller, 2012). During this time, both the people and government of China came to believe that the sole desire of European nations was to proselytize, addict, enslave, and colonize Asia just like Africa (Waley, 1958). Then, following the end of the Opium Wars, the Taiping Rebellion soon began. A civil war fueled by radical economic, political, and religious disruption, the masses attempted to overthrow the Qing Dynasty. Because the defeated rebels possessed a decidedly Christian disposition, this was seen as foreign religion directly challenging Chinese government and culture (Boardman, 1951). Additionally, this fear of Christianity was inevitably exacerbated near the end of the century during the Boxer Uprising when the Chinese grassroots launched attacks against oppressive foreigners. The Boxers, the secret society that initiated the revolution, was emphatically anti-Protestant (Rosaria, 2022). Both the Chinese government and people have had reason to oppose foreign religions during the last several hundred years.

The Chinese psyche still associates Christianity with bloody rebellion and instability. The modern recitation of these historical experiences consistently presents violence, oppression, entanglement, and invasion as inherent to foreign religions (Sneller, 2012). China is rightfully fearful of international religion and even more fearful of the pattern of consequences connected to foreign entanglement. This preoccupation that foreign nations are going to utilize religion to destabilize China permeates and governs the Chinese Communist Party's restriction of religion.

Culture of Collectivism

The instability of China's last 200 years has also left a legacy of cultural collectivism and intense nationalism. With foreign entanglement and radical revolution perceived as major instigators of societal instability, China has developed an inclusive, nationalistic mindset wary of outsiders (Deal, 2013). China is much more collectivistic than Western nations. As shown in Figure 3, on an Individuality scale of 1 to 100, with 50 being the average among nations, China is highly collectivistic with a score of 20 (Hofstede, 2022). Chinese people care about group dynamics; they strive to build tight-knit in-groups and are especially suspicious of anything that is perceived as external or unfamiliar. Foreign, international, and imported ideologies, cultures, and information are automatically contested as potentially damaging to group-unity (Waley, 1958). Where Western culture might be used to promoting individuality and self-reliance, Chinese culture prizes "interdependence," "reliance," and "loyalty" more than

"individuality," "freedom," and "liberty" (Hofstede, 2022).

Collectivism is evidenced in many aspects of Chinese society. Politics and government promote nationalism, unity, and a strong middle kingdom (Sewell, 2013). Economic directives remain focused on "collective morality needed for the accumulation of national material wealth" (Zhang, 2014). Regarding professional working relationships, "in-group considerations affect hiring and promotions" (Hofstede, 2022). Collectivism is even evidenced in the structure of the Chinese Constitution, itself; individual rights are only mentioned after the protection of the Chinese Communist Party, party leadership, socialism, and military might (People's Republic of China Const. art. XXXVI). Predictably, foreign religious ideas are met with extreme caution by both the government and people of China.

Figure 3
Hofstede Country Comparison of Individualism and Collectivism

Case-study: The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints

The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints (hereafter referred to as "the LDS Church") is not one of the five state-sanctioned religions in China. However, it operates in China and has done so for many years. While the complicated SARA application for state-sanction has not been approved, China tolerates and permits the Church operate under reasonable regulations (Evans, 2012). In other words, the LDS Church is operating in the Gray Market (Yang, 2006), neither fully sanctioned nor explicitly restricted but legitimately permitted. While the LDS Church refrains from publishing data and statistics on membership in China, it has publicly acknowledged Church participation among a small percentage of the Chinese

population (Chen, 2022).

The LDS Church maintains genial relations with the government of China and retains a reputation of integrity. For example, as publicly stated by Church President Russell M. Nelson in response to rumors of sending missionaries to China, the LDS Church has repeatedly promised only to enter China “through the front door. We do not go in through the back door or via the alley. Our relationships are based on honesty, openness, integrity, and complete compliance with local law” (Evans, 2012).

As a case-study, the LDS Church provides insights into the best strategic communication practices for international religions attempting to navigate “religious freedom with Chinese characteristics.” When comprehended and practiced, Communication Theory, Fundamental Attribution Error, theories of translation, and Uncertainty Reduction Theory advise foreign religions how to effectively advocate and showcase their organizations in China.

Figure 4
Church Membership by Region

Rule by Law & Communication Theory

Communication Theory, as described by Ruler (2018) argues that communication is “an ongoing process of meaning construction...a process that is interactive by nature and participatory at all levels.” Foreign religion in China has a dubious history fraught with communication characterized by unidirectional proselytizing (Cao, 2018). Although the LDS Church does not currently proselytize in mainland China, missionaries from the LDS Church first arrived in 1853 (Chen, 2020). And Christian missionaries have proselytized in China since the 6th century (Bays, 2012).

Religious groups have historically dug in their heels when facing rule by law in China, attempting to compel the government to acknowledge their legitimacy (Pittman, 2022). However, instead of browbeating and pressuring, foreign churches should seek open dialogic

processes, using “omnidirectional [and] agile management” of communication (Ruler, 2018).

The LDS Church has begun this conversational process, spanning organizational, educational, and even governmental dimensions. Interactions in the realm of higher education include BYU performance tours beginning in 1979 (Hilton III & Liu, 2016), BYU-Hawaii Polynesian Cultural Center collaborations (Church News Archives, 1989), and even guest lectures on open-heart surgery by Church leaders at Shandong University (Chen, 2020). In January 1989, Chinese Communist Party officials were invited to visit and tour Church Headquarters to increase understanding of The LDS Church and begin dialogue between leaders (Chen, 2020). Church leaders continue to promote second-language acquisition among its membership to increase intercultural understanding (Chen, 2020). And in 2010, talks were initiated by an unnamed senior official of the People’s Republic of China where Church leaders and Communist Party officials met to “regularize” relations (Askar, 2010) and ensure Church members are practicing “within the boundaries of Chinese law” (Brown, M. H., 2010). As dialogue and discourse continue to grow, both sides are listening.

The LDS Church must remember, Communication Theory promotes the idea of “meaning creation” occurring through reciprocal interaction and cooperation. Rather than dictating to the Chinese Communist Party the way it should govern, an intelligent approach would include listening to the needs of the people and government of China and co-creating a synergistic symbiotic relationship. This might look like the LDS Church acknowledging it operates under cultural constructs influenced by the rule of law and seeking assistance to discover how this cultural ideology functions in China. Moreover, instead of restlessly criticizing state-proclaimed atheism, Church members would do well to learn and inquire in order to escape premature condemnation.

Fundamental Attribution Error

Regarding the human predisposition to disagree with the ‘other,’ another theory is important to investigate: Fundamental Attribution Theory (Botan, 2017). Fundamental Attribution Error (FAE) refers to the natural tendency to ascribe others’ poor choices to their character or personality but our own poor choices to situation or circumstance. For example, if someone cuts me off in traffic then they are a jerk, but if I cut someone off it is because I had to make my exit. FAE is about discarding accountability and blaming others in order to prevent feeling guilty (Botan, 2017).

In the context of “religious freedom with Chinese characteristics,” Western literature regarding China is rife with FAE. It condemns nearly everything Chinese (communism, religious restriction, nationalism) as malevolently motivated while ignoring similar acts of nationalism in the West. This FAE not only frustrates productive intercultural communication but misrepresents reality. Decrying atheism without taking the time to learn their stories could be categorized as FAE just like condemning Christians without hearing their stories. International religions must recognize and minimize FAE. Successful religions will be patient in providing space, time, and communication to resolve these nearly inescapable inclinations. Continual learning coupled with self-awareness on both sides will provide the circumstances in which an international religion can develop in the realm of “religious freedom with Chinese characteristics.”

Theories of Translation

International religions must combat the concept of foreign oppression embedded in the Chinese psyche. How communication is translated is one key to accomplishing this (Nida, 1991). Churches must devote sufficient resources to proper translation in order to effectively break down the Chinese perspective of “other-ness” (Thompson, 2019). The nature and complexity of various translation strategies, in and of itself, makes this challenging. Add centuries of ideological disparity and miscommunication is bound to occur. As stated by Israelson-Hartley (2010), “missionaries and priests have struggled for centuries to teach Christian concepts to a polytheistic society that has no underlying concept of Jesus Christ.”

Despite the LDS Church’s meticulous attention to translation (Stringham, 1981), misunderstandings have and continue to occur. For example, the name of the Book of Mormon, principle scripture of the LDS Church, as originally translated unwittingly possessed similarities to “devil’s gate” in Mandarin, invoking a cultish feeling (Chen, 2020). A communicative approach to translation states that language should not be translated at the expense of meaning (Nida, 1991). “Language is nothing more than a vehicle” (Mathieu, 2015). Since that first translation, the name of the scriptures and Church have been retranslated (Chen, 2020), and the logo and name of The LDS Church circulated around the world (2011, Niebergall).

Additionally, permission for conference addresses to be presented in native languages (Walch, 2014b) precipitated Sam Chi Wong, an area authority of The LDS Church in China, to

present his world-wide broadcast address in Cantonese (Walch, 2014a). The LDS Church is making efforts to honor the language and culture of its members in China. The LDS Church should continue to allocate sufficient means to promote effective translation and increasingly allow natives to use their national languages.

Figure 5
Logo and Name of The LDS Church in English and Mandarin

Uncertainty Reduction Theory

Although largely believed to be an American religion, more than half the membership of the LDS Church is outside of the United States (Olsen & Otterstrom, 2019). However, the LDS Church is still widely perceived as stringently “committed to its American heritage and character (Hall, 2014). While there is nothing inherently wrong in remaining rooted in one’s own heritage, it is important that the LDS Church’s collectivism does not clash with China’s collectivism. Misunderstanding resulting from mistranslation, lack information, and misinterpretation has engendered a perspective of hostility toward the LDS Church that amplifies the conflict between Chinese nationalism and Church loyalty. In reality, both groups share similar devotion to collectivistic culture. For example, both the Chinese Communist Party and the LDS Church promote: supporting local and regional leaders, obeying laws, building community, societal harmony and contribution, and principles of conformity, loyalty, and allegiance (Deng, 1978; Evans 2012; He 2001; Qiao Collective, 2021; Thompson, 2019).

As the LDS Church continues to exemplify these principles, the Chinese government and people will become more familiar with them and recognize cultural similarities. Uncertainty Reduction Theory suggests that human beings are uncomfortable with the unknown and seek information to minimize cognitive and behavioral uncertainty (Botan, 2017). Acknowledging and honoring this theory, the LDS Church should actively seek to increase reciprocal familiarity. For example, a study completed in Hong Kong showed that Church member participation was positively correlated

with the member's previous experiences in similar Christian religions (Plüss, 2008). In other words, those who were already familiar with Christian culture were more consistent and active in the LDS Church after joining.

Strategies utilized by the LDS Church to promote awareness in other international circumstances might be helpful here: promoting LDS Charities by teaming up with local humanitarian and governmental organizations (Oliphant, 2016); inviting government leaders to visit Church Headquarters to meet with church leadership (Chen, 2020); sending volunteers to assist in second-language acquisition and English language learning (Hansen, 2012); and encouraging higher education discourse (Hilton III & Liu, 2016). However, perhaps the most visible promotion of familiarity—sending full-time missionaries to proselytize—has been restricted by the Chinese government (Evans, 2012); because of China's rule by law, the LDS Church should continue to honor this request, displaying trust and responsibility.

Conclusion

While the West condemns China for draconian religious repression (Human Rights Watch, 2022), there is space in which international religions can flourish. The history, culture, and context of the People's Republic of China has created the emergence of "religious freedom with Chinese characteristics" motivated by societal stability. As seen by analyzing The LDS Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, international religions can effectively operate and develop in China by: respecting the differences between rule of law and rule by law; promoting omnidirectional dialogue as described in Communication Theory; recognizing and minimizing Fundamental Attribution Error; allocating sufficient resources to effective translation; and employing Uncertainty Reduction Theory to promote reciprocal familiarity. International religions can be successful if they effectively utilize these strategic communication principles while operating within "religious freedom with Chinese characteristics."

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